

[HE ARA MAURI ORA]

TE KINAKINA WETLANDS

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in collaboration with

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ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof, angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

max. ceiling height open = open

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DAY 2: ~~SATURDAY~~ FRIDAY AT TEKAHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clear plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXTERNAL AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller parallel span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

roof reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof, angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

4m max. ceiling height open = open (CUBE SIDE OPENING)

roof over ceiling m/ah space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED DECK

DESIGN ITERATION

[INTRODUCTION]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACE

STRUCTURE

EXTERNAL AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller parallel span
CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

[TE KINAKINA]

Māi i Taumata-ō-Apanui ki Pōtaka

Ko Whanokao te maunga

Ko Mōtū te awa

Ko Whakaari te puia

Ko Apanui te tangata

Ko Te Whānau-ā-Apanui te iwi

Tihei mauri ora!

From Te Taumata-ō-Apanui to Pōtaka

Whanokao is the mountain

Mōtū is the river

Whakaari is the volcano

Apanui is the ancestor

Te Whānau-ā-Apanui is the tribe

The breath of life!

[TE KINAKINA]

Te Kaha No. 2C2 (also known as Te Kinakina) is a block of Māori freehold land situated on Copenhagen Road near the township of Te Kaha in the Eastern Bay of Plenty. The block comprises 22.68 hectares, jointly owned by six siblings of the Tukaki-Morrison whānau and encompasses a variety of terrains, including lowlands designated for wetlands as well as elevated, flatter areas currently in pasture and cultivation, punctuated by two intersecting valleys that cross the whenua. The Pakarunui Stream meanders through the northern portion of the site, through to the Te Kaha coastline and the Bay of Plenty.

Anchoring the block is a homestead tracing back to the 1930s, complemented by additional buildings including a studio space and visitor accommodation. The whenua has a rich history, having been under a long-term farming lease before only recently being returned to the Tukaki-Morrison whānau, symbolizing a connection to the past and a commitment to its sustainable and meaningful future. In November 2018, at a whānau hui in Te Kaha, whānau unanimously agreed to restore Te Kinakina wetlands and for Kathleen to lead this project.

[PROJECT AIM]

He ara mauri ora re-imagines a 'wetlands walkway' into a transformative and multi-purpose space that embodies Te Ao Māori values and universal access. Through engaging conversations with whānau, this project confronts the need for a design that intertwines accessibility, inclusivity, and play. The outcomes go beyond the pathway, including a whare toi/arts studio and accessible kāinga.

[SITE OVERVIEW]

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof, angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

max. ceiling height open = open

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DAY 2: SATURDAY FRIDAY AT TEKHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clean pasiva loggiate

10m - 12m

EXTERIOR AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller parallel span

PROGRAM - DISABILITY

altering roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

roof reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof, angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

4m max. ceiling height open = open (COBBLE SIDE OPENING)

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DESIGN ITERATION

[SITE ANALYSIS]

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller parallel span

PROGRAM - DISABILITY

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACE

SERVICES

EXTERIOR AREA

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

Tidal variability

Wharfedale Bay

Looking out to Wharfedale

To opaline

Secondary prevailing wind

Dominant prevailing wind

Erosion/drainage access

Potential car park site

COPPINWOOD ROAD

To opaline

[SKETCH ANALYSIS]

An initial desktop investigation of the site highlighted a range of physical site factors that would need to be considered in the design work, including the location of wetland ponds and the Pakarunui Stream, important trees, prevailing coastal winds, the large elevation change between the wetlands and elevated paddocks on site, and the generous solar access that the wetlands area enjoys.

[TE AO MĀORI CONTEXT]

TE KINAKINA MAURI

The design shows an array of different aspects of the wetlands, starting from the outside.

The outside red circle is showing the reach of the whakapapa of Tūkākī and the whānau, pulling back into the whenua from where we all come from.

The texture is to highlight the invertebrates, who are the true Kaitiaki of the wetlands.

The two darker curves are sun paths over the wetlands.

The bottom half is the description of what happened when Whānau-ā-Apanui was in Te Kaha, the rich kaimoana and the whales who inhabit the lands around.

[TE AO MĀORI CONTEXT]

BROTHERS OF WHĀNAU Ā APANUI

This work is the whakapapa of Whānau ā Apanui, the four sons of Tūkākī who each lead in different ways (Kaiao the farmer, Te Ehutū whenua leader, Tamahae the warrior and Ruatārehu).

The design is describing the wind behind Whānau-ā-Apanui waka, leading to the way to where we are today.

BIO-PHYSICAL

SOCIO-CULTURAL

WATER CATCHMENT

In stormy situation there is silt run-off downstream of Pakarano Stream.

we were at rising and falling levels in pakarano stream

minimal topographical change on site of walkway, but some in surrounding valley

+ REGIONAL AND LOCAL COUNCIL BOUNDARIES

Opoitiki district council

Bay of Plenty regional council

REGULATORY

+ RECORD OF TITLE

298 Copenhagen Road, Te Kaha, BOP, 3199, NZL.

Māori Freehold land, Te Kaha zc2

61 shares to 6 allocated owners, 226839 m², 56 acres, Waitiki district.

+ LAND USE

half site is arable (agriculture)

other half is lifestyle / mixed land use

This is where art studio is located

Opoitiki district

Council classifies as coastal residential zone

ANALYSIS]

Wes Tram council, etc...

+ OPOITIKI DISTRICT COUNCIL

controlled activities w/ resource consent

+ BUILDING PERFORMANCE

"Residential Bol barrier not req. For garden ponds & similar water hazards not intended to be used as a pool".

council control

max. 40% building site coverage

9m max. building height

min. 25m distance of building to stream with 3m aver. width or more. 10m if less.

1x parking space per 20 m² of activity area.

1.1 m² maximum signage for community recreation activities

Storm water, waste water, freshwater provisions

design + appearance

effect on water bodies

vegetation, archaeological site impact.

public toilets

community and recreation activities that exceed 100 m²

HAZARD MAPS

whole site is in tsunami evac. zone

site intersects coastal env. zone and indigenous biological diversity space

art studio building site is located on Waiaapu strong sand (Wog) rest of site is TE KAHU sandy loam (TEK)

[DIGITAL SITE MODEL]

SCULPTING
SITE

APPLYING SATELLITE
IMAGERY

PREPARING FILE TO
BE CNC CUT

Contour data accessed via the Bay of Plenty Council open interactive mapping software was used to develop an accurate topographical site model. Satellite imagery was then used to locate the Pakaranui stream, the driveway, power lines, roads and buildings.

[PHYSICAL SITE MODEL]

*FOAM BOARD SCULPTED BY
CNC MACHINE*

*PAINTED AND
ETCHED*

FINAL SITE MODEL

The site model was scaled down to roughly 800x400mm and used to produce a physical site model. The topography and site features were etched from a gold foam block using a CNC machine. The model was then painted and small pieces of timber and fishing line were used to locate the low voltage power lines.

[SITE VISIT]

In December 2023, the team travelled to Te Kinakina to meet Kathleen and Violet, observe the site in person and conduct the whānau-hui.

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

max ceiling height open = open

look over ceiling into space

~~# DAY 2: SATURDAY~~ ~~FRIDAY AT TEKAHA~~

OPERABLE WINDOW

clear plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller Porcelain Span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

look reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

4m max ceiling height open = open (COULDE SIDE OPENING)

look over ceiling into space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED CEILING

DESIGN ITERATION

[WHĀNAU HUI & INTERVIEWS]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACES

SERVICES

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller Porcelain Span

CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

[TE KINAKINA HUI]

On Saturday 16th December, we held a luncheon and whānau hui on-site at Te Kinakina. This included whānau hauā (carers looking after whānau members with disabilities) as well as disability service providers. The aim of the hui was to capture ideas and aspirations for the walkway, kāinga and arts studio that we could explore and incorporate into the designs.

Follow-up interviews were held between January-March 2024 with whānau who were interested in the project but were unable to attend the hui in December.

[CAPTURING IDEAS]

A2 PAGE IDEA BOARD

Using post-it notes, we captured a range of ideas from our hui as we spoke to different whānau members, sticking the notes to large blank pages to make a clear, visual summary.

A1 AERIAL PHOTOS

Large aerial photos of Te Kinakina on the tables helped us to contextualise the project. Whānau were able to suggest specific design ideas relative to certain parts of the site, such as connecting with the Pakarunui Stream.

SITE MODEL

The physical site model helped illustrate changes of elevation across the whenua and brought a vertical dimension to supplement the aerial photos.

[KEY QUOTES]

Te Kinakina is set within an Indigenous, tribal landscape. Several whānau members suggested whakataukī as pathway signposts. Whakataukī offer instructions for living and wellbeing, an explanation for the way things are, and a structure and introduction to every experience that the wetlands have to offer.

Others reflected on personal experiences and connections with the whenua:

"[It would be good for the pathway] to go to the [pūriri] tree in winter because you can see the green pūriri moths, they used to fly up to the window, lots of them. It was the same time the frogs would come. We used to get frogs in springtime...Tom would dig fence post holes and frogs would be in the holes the next day...there are still a few old people left [who would] like to ponder along...and share stories about the olden days..."

"A lot of people who genuinely know this place, have stories about this place."

In approaching the design, whānau offered a range of practical considerations that needed to be woven into the design to work for a range of abilities and needs:

"...there needs to be some form of seat. People might need to rest. But it might even just be that I just want to sit here for 20 minutes and contemplate, and enjoy it"

"With older people, and I think of my mother, it's thinking about things like handrails...something all the way around. And places that they can just rest, and get up again. Because this is quite a big space for people to walk..."

"...one of the things I suggested is somewhere on the walkway, having a quiet space. That might be like a bus stop, where I could go and sit and not feel anxious..."

"My child loves the sound of the wheels of her pram on wood. Or the crunching of gravel. But then someone who wants less stimulation might just want a nice concrete path or something similar."

[KEY QUOTES]

We were introduced to the relevant building standard, NZS 4121, with helpful advice that this is the bare minimum for accessible design:

"...go back to Building Standard 4121. That's the minimum standard, but it's old and it needs updating...you need to think about it as a starting point, and think what else you could add...then you're actually future-proofing it."

"If I'm pushing someone in a manual wheelchair, I don't want it to be too hard. [A gradient of] 12:1 is the minimum. But make it better than that." –

Te Kinakina could help re-frame the notion of a pathway from one of containment (necessary to keep tamariki safe) to a pathway of participation and engagement, by offering multi-sensory experiences:

"...a lot of these interactive things can be built into the rail [of the walkway], so you don't actually see it as a barrier. You see it as the interaction."

"Just the opportunity to feel like you're participating in the environment [is such a good thing]. You're not just watching it. You've got viewing spaces where you can see stuff happening..."

[KEY QUOTES]

It came back to having options that work for everyone, irrespective of their individual circumstances:

"It's about having options for every age and stage."

"...what you've gotta think about too is that, yes we're talking about people with disabilities, but we're also talking about people that are ageing. In the next 30 years, you've got the silver tsunami, in the nicest possible way."

As well as important contributions to design ideas, whānau reflected on the participatory process as key to the project too:

"What a privilege to have been asked to come today...spectacular venue, spectacular kai...but also to be included around the table. I see this as a privilege to be at the ground floor...we would like to stand beside you on this journey going forward, thank you so much for today."

"This project is so cool, honestly...this could be life-changing for some of our community. Just being able to have a space that they can go to, like...yeah. Cos we don't have anywhere we can like, de-stress and...you know, just...just 'be'. Without judgement."

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

max. ceiling height open = open

roof overhanging main space

DAY 2: SATURDAY FRIDAY AT TEKAHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clean plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXTERNAL AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller parallel span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

roof reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

4m max. ceiling height open = open (COBBLE SIDE OPENING)

roof overhanging main space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED AREA

DESIGN ITERATION

[DESIGN FRAMEWORK]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACE

STRUCTURE

EXTERNAL AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller parallel span

CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOOR

1-5m

[ESTABLISHED FRAMEWORK]

This project is guided by the following principles that we collated from the whānau hui and interviews.

MĀTAURANGA

The project is to enhance and develop whenua based education, enabling connection to indigenous knowledge.

KAITIAKITANGA

Te Kinakina wetlands is to be built for the long term, restoring the wetlands to it's historic state prior to 1967.

ŌRITETANGA

The designs need to be universally designed. It must grant users simple, flexible, intuitive and appropriate spaces.

[INITIAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS - STUDIO]

Once the second half of the research began, it was important to organise all of the driving forces behind the studio building in order to ensure they're achieved in the design.

[DESIGN FRAMEWORK - STUDIO]

The studio outcomes and kaupapa Māori framework were combined to create the basis for judging the studio building's success.

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

max ceiling height open = open

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DAY 2: SATURDAY FRIDAY AT TEKAHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clear plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller Porcelain Span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

look reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

4m max ceiling height open = open (CUBE SIDE OPENING)

roof over ceiling m/ah space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED DECK

DESIGN ITERATION

[CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT - PATHWAY]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPEN DECK SPACE

SERVICES

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller Porcelain Span

CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

[OVERVIEW]

This render provides a comprehensive view of the wetlands, highlighting all its features.

The grand, majestic entry seamlessly transitions into a sleek pathway that integrates with Te Kinakina, enhancing the natural beauty of the wetlands without detracting from it.

[CAR PARKING]

This render showcases the entry to the wetlands and the adjacent parking spaces.

The design creates a dynamic experience as you walk through, with views that are alternately concealed and revealed, leading seamlessly onto the pathway.

[HAUMIA AT NIGHT]

This render depicts the wetland entry at night, prominently located along the Haumiatiketike track, where you are positioned right beside the water.

[THE BRIDGE]

The Pūrākau of Maui and Tunaroa is illustrated through the two sides, showcasing both salt-water and freshwater eels. The difference is evident in their broad faces and varying heights.

The left side represents freshwater eels, navigating upstream with impressive leaps, while the shorter right bridge symbolizes salt-water eels, undulating through the waves like sea conger eels. These are separated by the pathway, symbolizing Maui.

[POUHUTUKAWA SEATING]

The seating around the Pōhutukawa is inspired by the Pōhutukawa trees found along the coastal area, emerging from the rocks. The seating appears to organically span out from the wood, as if it has always been a part of the whenua.

This design ensures accessibility for a diverse range of people by featuring different heights to accommodate various needs. The seating's playful, yet functional, height variations are seamlessly integrated into a simple, curved design.

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

max ceiling height open = open

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DAY 2: SATURDAY FRIDAY AT TEKAHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clear plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller Porcelain Span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

look reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

4m max ceiling height open = open (CUBE SIDE OPENING)

roof over ceiling m/ah space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED DECK

DESIGN ITERATION

[CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT - STUDIO]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPEN DECK SPACE

SERVICES

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller Porcelain Span

CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

[FLOOR PLAN IT.1]

This is the first design move made toward creating the studio building. Violet and Ben sketched out the basic form and spacial organisation of the studio building so we could visualise the space.

[FLOOR PLAN IT.2]

Immediately after the initial sketch, Ben produced a more refined version that noted all the important features violet had mentioned in their discussion.

[FLOOR PLAN IT.3]

Once we returned to Wellington, Ben produced a more refined drawing of the studio building which included proximity to the walkway, some dimensions and new developments.

[CONTEXT SKETCH]

This drawing was made to situate the studio in relation to the pathway and wetland, as well as to visualise the building in section for the first time.

[SECTION EXPLORATION]

Section developments continued and were used to explore potential roof lines for the studio building. The red box indicates the roof line which inspired the final design.

[DETAIL EXPLORATION]

Once the general form was decided, Ben began to explore detail moments around the building, including horizontal load resistance and balustrade detailing.

[STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS]

NZ3604 Timber structure guide was consulted and approximations of structural element sizing were made. These members include; posts, bearers, floor joists, bottom + top plates, studs, dwangs, lintels, sills, ceiling joists and rafters.

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

max. ceiling height open = open

look over ceiling into space

~~# DAY 2: SATURDAY~~ ~~FRIDAY AT TEKAHA~~

OPERABLE WINDOW

clean plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXTERIOR AREA

monopitch roof

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller parallel span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

look reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Timber running through to outdoor covered area

4m max. ceiling height open = open (COBBLE SIDE OPENING)

look over ceiling into space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED AREA

DESIGN ITERATION

[DEVELOPED DESIGN - STUDIO]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACE

STRUCTURE

EXTERIOR AREA

monopitch roof

Smaller parallel span

CLADDING ELEVATION

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOOR

1-5m

[FLOOR PLAN]

- 1 Open plan studio space - furniture is non-indicative of use.
- 2 Kitchenette covered by bi-fold screen with wheel chair accessible bench space.
- 3 All abilities WC fitted with shower, change table, height adjustable basin, accessible toilet and hand-rails.
- 4 Second WC fitted with toilet and basin.
- 5 Open deck space sheltered with timber screen at corners.
- 6 Pathway access to studio building.

CONCEPT ONLY

[SW ELEVATION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[NW ELEVATION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[NE ELEVATION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[SE ELEVATION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[CROSS SECTION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[LONG SECTION]

CONCEPT ONLY

[CONNECTION TO PATHWAY]

[EYE-LEVEL VIEW]

[DECK AREA]

[STUDIO]

[STUDIO APPROACH]

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

max ceiling height open = open

roof over ceiling m/ah space

DAY 2: ~~SATURDAY~~ FRIDAY AT TEKHA

OPERABLE WINDOW

clear plastic louvre

10m - 12m

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller Porcelain Span

PROGRAM FOR DISABILITY

8m SPAN DIMENSIONS

adjusting roof angle

OVERLAP EXPLORATION

look reaching down to floor

ROOF-LINE EXPLORATION

roof angle, looking ground

Test sunning through to outdoor code cases

4m max ceiling height open = open (COULDE SIDE OPENING)

roof over ceiling m/ah space

SHADE SPACE

COVERED CEILING

DESIGN ITERATION

[MOVING FORWARD]

OPERABLE WINDOW

OPENING SPACES

STRUCTURE

EXPERIMENTAL AREA

ART STUDIO
CLADDING ELEVATION

Smaller Porcelain Span

TIMBER SUIT BENCH SEAT

BENCH SEAT OVERLAP EXPLORATION

TIMBER FLOORING

1-5m

NEWS

ALL ACCESS: Kathleen Morrison, Matt Lloyd, Violet Aydon-Pou, Oscar McConaughy, Ben Siesicki and Dr James Berghan are working together on making Te Kinakina wetland accessible for all-ability people. Photos Sven Carlsson E4277-6

Wetland readies for the next step

Sven Carlsson

A Kāi and korero event was held at Te Kinakina wetlands in Te Kaha on Saturday.

The meeting was hosted by landowner Kathleen Morrison and her partner, Violet Aydon-Pou, who together are spearheading the transformation of the former dairy farm into a 7-hectare wetland.

Having last year received a \$50,000 grant from BayTrust to help with the construction of a 1.6-kilometre deer fence to protect the property, the two women are in the process of realising the next stages of the project.

This includes not only more planting and predator control, but making the Copenhagen Road-based wetland a community resource.

Ms Morrison said they were "designing for inclusion, and creating spaces for all-ability people in Te Kinakina wetlands".

To that effect, Dr James Berghan from the school of Architecture at Wellington's Victoria University, has visited Te Kinakina with three of his students to help produce design solutions.

Dr Berghan has secured summer scholarships for the three students to help design the all-abilities pathway, an all-abilities art studio, as well as conceptual designs for connected, climate-resilient homes that will accommodate all-ability people, Ms Morrison said.

The students, Matt Lloyd, Ben Siesicki and Oscar McConaughy, had prepared a three-dimensional model of the wetland and had questions and maps ready for the visitors to

encourage both understanding and queries.

Community representatives, families with special-needs members and professionals were invited to attend the weekend meeting.

Erinwyn Cox, from the Disabilities Resource Centre in Whakatāne, was there with her colleague, Naomi Freeman, and Drew Manning, from the Maori Achievement Collaborative, also attended.

Cox made many suggestions on how the architect could construct the all-inclusive pathway and rest areas.

These included following a specific building standard and improving upon it with considerations for tactile experiences, seat heights, dimensions required for electrical wheelchair users, sensory spaces and how to make accommodations for the vision impaired.

Mr Manning spoke about something similar that had been done at Allandale School in Whakatāne, where he was previously a principal.

"It was not only about education, but also engagement space for the community," he said.

The school's special area included a barbecue, sensory garden and places for a variety of physical activities.

"It was fantastic, learning through play - it cut down on behavioural problems," Mr Manning said.

"The kids could find spaces that fit them." Mr Manning said he was very interested in the Te Kinakina all access project.

DIGGING PONDS: Ponds are created for the wetland in March 2021. E4277-1

FENCED: Kinakina becomes a real wetland. E4277-2

WETLAND MODEL: Kathleen Morrison talks to Ben Siesicki, James Berghan and Oscar McConaughy, about plans for the wetland. E4277-3

[ŌPŌTIKI NEWS ARTICLE]

A local journalist and videographer who attended the first whānau hui wrote and article regarding the current Te Kinakina project and aspirations for future works.

[2WALK & CYCLE CONFERENCE]

In March of 2024, James, Ben, Matt, and Oscar introduced the Te Kinakina project to an annual active transport conference in Te Whanganui-a-Tara, Wellington.

[SECOND WHĀNAU HUI]

In April of 2024, James and Ben returned to Te Kinakina to present the project works. Whānau had an opportunity to have a korero regarding the processes and outcomes of the cumulative work of all those involved.

This marks the current journey to date for He Ara Mauri Ora. The next steps involve funding applications for detailed design and consent processes.

National
SCIENCE
Challenges

National
SCIENCE
Challenges

AGEING
WELL

Kia eke kairangi ki te
taikaumātutanga

HEALTHIER
LIVES

He Oranga
Hauora

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TE HERENGA WAKA